

TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE AS A SECOND LANGUAGE

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Annotation: *This article reviews that teaching the English language to students with different first languages, typically used to imply that the English Language Learner may have already learned more than one language, prior to learning English.*

Key words: *English, foreign language, world language, teaching of modern languages, English-speaking*

Nowadays, English is used by at least one billion people around the world, either as a first or as a second language. Therefore, it is very much considerable to me to be a professional teacher who is aware of the modern methods of teaching English language as a foreign language. Keywords: English language, modern, computer, communication, student, teacher, method, technology, vocabulary, form of training. Teaching English as a Foreign Language is vital especially in the developing countries in which English is considered to be a foreign language. It is clear that people need better opportunities that they can only get with a good group of English. In Uzbekistan people who want to learn English have a great number of abilities to know this language. For teachers very important to listening good spoken English at your level of understanding will improve all aspects of your speaking, since we normally learn our first language by first listening and hearing it spoken by others. If you can understand English-language movies and programs, then listen to news and documentary programs, whose presenters tend to speak well. For easier work, practice listening to English instructional CDs, mp3s or computer software, at home or at a school language auditory. You can also find English-language radio, TV and instructional materials on the Internet. In the modern world we have much more opportunities to rich a language. Modern Methods of Teaching Listening Skills Effective, modern methods of teaching listening skills get everything from interactive exercises to multimedia resources. Listening skills are best learned through simple, understandable activities that focus more on the learning process than on the final product. Whether you are working with a large group of students or a small one, you can use any of the following examples to develop your own methods for teaching students how to

listen, write, read and speak well. Language education may take place as a general school subject or in a specialized language school. There are many methods of teaching languages. Some have fallen into history and others are widely used; still others have a small following, but offer useful. There is no doubt that English has become a universal language. Nowadays, English is used by at least one billion people around the world, either as a first or as a second language. Therefore, it is very much considerable to me to be a professional teacher who is aware of the modern methods of teaching English language as a foreign language. No one can ignore the need and the value of methods for teaching English as a foreign language or even as a second language. Students are different in their needs. Some students learn visually, others orally; others have shorter attention skills and all come from different backgrounds. To meet all their needs, it is necessary to use a wide range of methods. Some methods teacher may do with the help of different resources or create them by alone based at teaching experience. Contribute insights that may be absorbed into the generally accepted mix. Uses of modern technology in classroom teaching are very useful for learners. There are a lot of capacities to make a teaching process easy and productive. Nobody can deny that technology has improved education. Educators have also dramatically adjusted their teaching methods in response to new technology over the years. Many schools now carefully consider cost and application when debating how to best use new technology. In Uzbekistan teachers use computers or another technologies very often. Most of the lessons are not classical. As the result pupils who finish school can understand oral speech or have not any other problems with foreign language. Gadgets that are used strictly by teachers are designed to enhance presentations, help with book keeping or assist with outside 16 communications. Projection devices have become more affordable and now are nearly standard in many classrooms. Interactive whiteboards, although still expensive, provide an instant interface between the classroom and cyberspace, allowing teachers to transform lectures into real-time multimedia presentations. Although providing laptops for every student in the classroom is still cost-prohibitive for most school districts, wireless mobile labs can be used in group projects. These devices connect directly to the school's Internet access, and the signal is relayed to laptops that can be distributed to students. Individual word processors are now also becoming more affordable as well as smaller, hand-held devices such as personal digital assistants that can be hot-synced to the teacher's computer. Gadgets in the classroom can create a more interesting, interactive environment that students are mostly already familiar with outside school, except in the poorest districts. If schools strive to keep

current with technological trends and budget their priorities, then the learning that takes place becomes more relevant and meaningful to students [1, c. 38]. Computer literacy and knowledge of major software programs is no longer reserved for higher educational systems or special trade schools in today's society. Besides being cost-prohibitive, the constant maintenance and upgrading of classroom technology can put a strain on time that should be devoted to teaching and learning. Because of many crossover software packages that have been developed, Macintosh and Microsoft environments are gaining equal access into modern classrooms. Which platform educational decision-makers choose, the future remains unpredictable, and today's good buy may end up on tomorrow's junk heap of outdated technology

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